

USM hosts seminar on climate policy, coastal protection, vulnerable persons

POND ISLAND--The University of St. Martin (USM) recently concluded a two-day seminar and workshop titled "Climate Policy, Coastal Protection and Vulnerable Communities," held April 10-11. This regional initiative, organised in the framework of the Island(er)s at the Helm research programme, brought together climate adaptation experts, community leaders,

artists, scholars, and policymakers from across the Caribbean and beyond to explore sustainable, inclusive solutions to climate-related challenges in vulnerable communities.

With the involvement of 24 participants in person and over 70 participants from Aruba, Barbuda, Cuba, Curaçao, the Netherlands, Puerto Rico, Saba, St Maarten, Trinidad and

Tobago, Italy and Spain, and other countries across Europe, the event marked a significant step in cross-border dialogue and regional cooperation.

Keynote addresses were delivered by Dr. Ofelia Pérez from the Universidad de Oriente in Santiago de Cuba and Pedzi Flores-Girigori, Head of the Meteorology Office of Curaçao. Both speakers set the tone for in-depth, interdisciplinary discussions across six key themes: climate and vulnerability; policy and representation; voices of the vulnerable; Dutch Caribbean climate agendas; climate and the arts and human expression and water, food and shelter.

The opening ceremony featured remarks by Prime Minister and Minister of General Affairs, Dr. Luc Mercelina, and Minister of Public Housing, Spatial Planning, Infrastructure and Environment VROMI, Patrice Gumbs. Both dignitaries urged participants to move beyond sustainability rhetoric and work toward concrete, innovative, and regionally integrated climate solutions for the most vulnerable communities. Minister Gumbs emphasized the importance of breaking through silos to find integrated approaches, while Prime Minister Mercelina encouraged deeper Caribbean cooperation and inclusivity.

USM President Dr. Antonio Carmona Báez opened

Some of the persons involved in the USM seminar.

the event by reminding participants that climate change knows no borders and that it does not discriminate among independent countries and dependent territories. The university remains committed to fostering dialogue that transcends insular perspectives in the Caribbean.

Highlights from the two-day event included what USM said had been a thought-provoking first panel featuring Dr. Line Algoed who discussed the process of vulnerabilisation, linking historical colonial inequalities to contemporary risks, and Raymond Jessurun, USM Research Coordinator and co-coordinator of the St Maarten Anti-Poverty Platform, who offered grassroots insights into current vulnerabilities on the island.

A session titled Voices of the Vulnerable, spotlighting John Mussington, recently elected Chairman of the Barbuda Island Council, and Ashma Berkel of the local NGO Leaders for Change in St Maarten, both sharing community-based approaches to resilience building.

A panel on Policy and Representation, which included Mari Villariny Marrero of

the Association of Planners of Puerto Rico, VROMI Policy Officers Raitza Naran and Ildiko Gilders, and Bernadette Davis, Second Vice-President of the Collectivité de Saint-Martin, who stressed the need for inclusion of local voices in regional and international policy processes.

An artistic and intellectual exploration during the Climate and the Arts and Human Expression panel, with contributions from Clara Reyes, Head of the Department of Culture, discussing the poetic work of Deborah Jack, alongside local artist Claudio Arnell and postdoc researcher and musicologist Dr. Charissa Granger, who offered a Caribbean cultural lens through the thought of Sylvia Wynter.

The Dutch Caribbean Climate Agenda panel featured Dr. Timo Kelder of the Climate Adaptation Services (CAS), Delroy Delain and Colby Poerio of EPIC Sint Maarten, and highlighted the importance of community engagement in local environmental efforts.

Discussions on water, food and shelter included Dr. George Felix (University of Puerto Rico, Mayagüez), Aga Kus, a PhD researcher at Delft Technical University specializing in sustainable housing for Sint Maarten, and Dr. Alejandro Torres-Abreu, who remarked upon

the struggle for water justice in San Juan, Puerto Rico.

The seminar was made possible through the collaboration of USM, the Ministry of VROMI, the Collectivité de Saint-Martin, and various institutions and civil society organizations throughout the region. The presence of Vice-President Bernadette Davis of the Collectivité signalled a firm commitment to joint action across the island.

Day two of the seminar/workshop consisted of a series of exercises guided by Dr. Perez Monetero which led to the development of a tool to incorporate all stakeholders in community-born initiatives to influence climate policies. Participants included civil servants, representatives of NGOs, community leaders and USM students, who were equipped with the tools to engage the community in the process of policy making.

Through these two days of exchange, the University of St. Martin reaffirmed its role as a regional hub for education and research supporting policy in the face of the climate crisis. The event served as a launchpad for continued collaboration and innovation, centred on the lived realities and cultural strengths of Caribbean peoples.

Tax Admin. launches WhatsApp service

PHILIPSBURG--The Tax Administration has launched a WhatsApp service, designed to improve communication and provide taxpayers with a faster and more convenient way to contact the Tax Department.

This service will help taxpayers receive quick responses to general questions, get basic guidance on tax-related issues, and find the forms they need. This service will be available during regular office hours, Monday to Friday, from 8:00am to 2:00pm.

While existing communication methods such as email and phone are still available, the WhatsApp service adds another option, especially useful for urgent questions that require fast responses. Taxpayers with more complex questions or document-related requests and submissions are encouraged to continue using the official email address:

Taxinfo@sintmaartengov.org.

The introduction of this service reinforces the Tax Administration's commitment to improving public accessibility and responsiveness. In addition to the new WhatsApp service, taxpayers can continue to reach the department through the phone numbers +1 (721) 542-2143, 542-5301, 542-5304, 542-3839. To access the new WhatsApp service, simply save the number +1 (721) 556-3699 in your phone and send a message.

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